

76th Irish Universities Chemistry Research Colloquium

Report by: F. Heaney and D. Rooney

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– 17/06/2025

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Organising Committee: Sarah Bonham, Michelle Doran, Karen Herdman, Keane McNamee, Keela Kessie, Stephen Barrett, Barbara Woods, Denise Rooney, Frances Heaney

Chemistry Department, Maynooth University

Event Sponsors

RSC Local Section (Republic of Ireland), Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, Advion Interchim Scientific, Alltech Inc., Almac Group, Cruinn Diagnostics Ltd., Element Lab Solutions, Eurachem Ireland, Fluorochem Ltd., GPE Scientific, Henkel, Intel Corporation, Mason Technology, PerkinElmer, Scientific Laboratory Supplies, SSPC, Maynooth University

Summary

The Irish Universities Chemistry Research Colloquium, run under the aegis of the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland (ICI), has postgraduate research as its central focus. It is the longest-running scientific conference in Ireland. At this 76th event in the series, in a welcoming and supportive atmosphere post graduate students presented their research; there were 39 oral presentations as well as 18 flash and 83 poster presentations. There were also opportunities to discuss research more informally. All areas of chemistry were

covered with themed sessions in Medicinal and Organic Chemistry, Materials, Electrochemistry, Sustainable and Environmental Chemistry, Reaction Mechanisms and Computational Chemistry.

Dr Michelle Browne (Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie) and Prof Steven Bell (QUB) were inspiring Plenary Speakers and Dr Fionn McNeill (UCD) delivered the Institute of Chemistry of Ireland Dervilla Donnelly Postgraduate Award lecture.

A number of sponsors attended the meeting and some exhibited at stands throughout the event.

The ICI Young Chemists Network held its annual general meeting at the event, and a session on how to prepare for a PhD Viva, while a working lunch for Heads/Representatives of Chemistry Departments across Ireland took place.

Attendees

More than 200 delegates from 14 different Institutions across the Island of Ireland registered for this meeting.

Target audience: academics, postdoctoral researchers, undergraduate and postgraduate students, technical officers/support staff, industrial sponsors, professional body members (RSC, ICI, Eurachem), members of national scientific centres.

Programme

Table 1. Programme for 76th Irish Universities Chemistry Research Colloquium

Time	June 16th	
10.15-11.15	Plenary: Dr Michelle Browne Chair: Prof. Carmel Breslin	
11.15-11.45	Coffee Break and Poster Setup	
11.45-13.00	Electrochemistry Chair: Dr Constantina Paptriantafyllopoulou Domink Duleba (UCD) Rashma Kidayaveettill (Galway) Pei-Hsuan Wu (TCD) Rupa Ranjani Planisamy (UCC) Flash: Aoife Newman (MU), Robert Guest (UL), Catherine Noonan (Galway)	Medicinal Chemistry Chair: Dr Gavin D'Arcy Andrea Cislaru (MU) Aoife Cotter (UL) MounaHind Laiche (RCSI) Eleanor Windle (UCD) Flash: Ryan Madden (DCU), Fayanne Nolin (TCD), Jack Daly (UCC)
13.00-14.30	Lunch and ICI Young Chemists Network Meeting	
14.30-16.00	Materials Chemistry Chair: Dr Susan Kelleher Darragh McHugh (Galway) Francesca Adami (UCD) Julian Carolan (TCD) Liam Jowett (UCD) Flash: Anna Nakonechna (RCSI), Catherine Cleary (UL), Ciara Tobin (DCU)	Organic Synthesis Chair: Dr Stephen Barrett Zoe Byrne (UCD) Abinash Nayak (SETU) Aoife Martin (UCD) Adam McCormack (MU) Niamh Lehane (UCD) Flash: Amélia Laetitia Auville (UCD), Ben Mohan (Galway), Brian Durkin (RCSI)
16.00-16.15	Comfort Break	
16.15-17.15	Sustainable and Environmental Chemistry Chair: Dr Fergal Byrne Marilia Dalla Benetta (MU) Christine Coffey (UCD) Santiago Martinez Sosa (Galway) Flash: Krishna Hari (UL), Perveen Akhtar (TUD), Doireann O'Leary Brennan (UCC)	Reaction Mechanism, Computational Chemistry Chair: Dr Davide Tiana Adam Cruise (UCD) Matthew Murray (Galway) Ardra Karthika (Galway) Flash: Anja Gotzen (TCD), Eoghan Courtney (UCD), Daryl Rediy (MU)
17.15-18.45	Poster Session	
18.45	Social evening	

Time	June 17th	
09.30-10.30	Plenary: Prof. Steven Bell Chair: Prof. Declan Gilheany	
10.30-11.30	Materials Chemistry Chair: Dr Daniele Alves Viktorija Mikaite (UCD) Giada Diana (UL) Kathryn McCarthy (Galway) Joseph Monaghan (MU)	Organic Synthesis Chair: Dr Luke Brennan Oliwier Dulawa (MU) Parth Naik (UCD) Sebastian Pim (RCSI) Rachel Lynch (UCD)
11.30-12.00	Coffee Break	
12.00-13.00	Materials/ Electrochemistry Chair: Dr Sousa Javan Nikkah Shane O'Neill (UCD) Laura Coffey (UL) Levente Nagy (Galway) Olivia Breen (UCD)	Medicinal/Organic Chemistry Chair: Dr Laura Diaz Casado Federica Brescia (Galway) Amani Al Riyami (TCD) Vanessa Becker (UCD)
13.15-13.40	ICI Dervilla Donnelly Postgraduate Award Lecture: Fionn McNeill (UCD) Chair: Prof. Steven Bell (President, ICI)	
13.40-14.00	Prizegiving and Colloquium Closing Ceremony Prof. Steven Bell	

Prizes

Congratulations to all our oral, flash and poster presentation prize winners – Liam Jowett (UCD), Joseph Monahan (MU) Aoife Martin (UCD), Vanessa Becker (UCD), Matthew Murray (UoG), Katy Murray (State Lab/TUD), Anna Nakonechna (RCSI), Doireann O'Leary (UCC), Alessio Zavaroni (MU), Niamh Hickey (UL), Liam Casey (UCD), Ciara Tobin (DCU) and Anjan Gotzen (TCD)

Figure 1. Photograph of prize winners at the 76th Irish Universities Chemistry Research Colloquium at Maynooth University together with Professor Steven Bell, President Institute of Chemistry of Ireland

Acknowledgements

Thanks are extended to all who attended and participated in the 76th Chemistry Colloquium and to the sponsors that made the event happen! Particular thanks to those who chaired sessions and judged oral and poster sessions. We acknowledge the help of all volunteers and MU professional service staff who dedicated their time and effort to make the event a success.